

Multi-frequency GNSS Robust Carrier Tracking for Ionospheric Scintillation Mitigation

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ABSTRACT

Ionospheric scintillation is the physical phenomena affecting radio waves propagating from the space through the ionosphere to earth. The signal distortion induced by scintillation can pose a major threat to some GNSS application. Scintillation is one of the more challenging propagation scenarios, particularly affecting high-precision GNSS receivers which require high quality carrier phase measurements; and safety critical applications which have strict accuracy, availability and integrity requirements. Under ionospheric scintillation conditions, GNSS signals are affected by fast amplitude and phase variations, which can compromise the receiver synchronization. To take into account the underlying correlation among different frequency bands, we propose a new multivariate autoregressive model (MAR) for the multi-frequency ionospheric scintillation process. Multi-frequency GNSS observations and the scintillation MAR are modeled in state-space, allowing independent tracking of both line-of-sight phase variations and complex gain scintillation components. The resulting joint synchronization and scintillation mitigation problem is solved using a robust nonlinear Kalman filter, validated using real multi-frequency scintillation data with encouraging results.

Key words. GNSS – ionospheric scintillation – multivariate AR modeling – robust tracking – carrier phase synchronization – adaptive nonlinear Kalman filter

1. Introduction

Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) is the technology of choice for most position-related applications when it is available ([Dardari et al., 2015](#)). A GNSS receiver relies on a constellation of satellites to estimate a set of range measures from which to compute its position. The main challenges of GNSS technology arise when operating in complex, harsh propagation scenarios which are naturally impaired by multipath, shadowing, high dynamics, or ionospheric scintillation. In the

31 last decade, ushered by an ever increasing demand for availability, accuracy, and reliability, the mit-
32 igation of these challenges has steered intense research on advanced receiver design (Amin et al.,
33 2016).

34 Among these challenges, in this paper we focus on ionospheric scintillation. Because such distur-
35 bance is not related to the local environment, as in the case of multipath or shadowing, it can degrade
36 receiver performance even under ideal open-sky conditions. Ionospheric scintillation is caused by a
37 disturbance in the portion of the ionosphere through which the GNSS signals propagates, an effect
38 particularly relevant in polar and equatorial regions. It can produce rapidly varying constructive and
39 destructive interference between multiple scattered signals. This turbulent behavior can render the
40 carrier phase difficult to track by the receiver. One of the major challenges of severe scintillation
41 propagation conditions is known as canonical fading, which is characterized by a combination of
42 strong fading and rapid phase changes in a simultaneous and random manner (Kintner et al., 2009;
43 Humphreys et al., 2009). From a synchronization standpoint, measuring the signal phase during
44 such a fade is very challenging because rate of change of phase changes is at its highest when the
45 signal amplitude is near its lowest (Humphreys et al., 2005). This may lead the receiver to momen-
46 tarily lose carrier synchronization, resulting in either cycle-slips or loss of lock. Unfortunately, the
47 accuracy improvement of modern high-precision receivers is based on the use of carrier phase-based
48 positioning techniques, and so it is extremely sensitive to scintillation perturbations (Jacobsen and
49 Dähnn, 2014; Prikryl et al., 2014; Banville and Langley, 2013; Banville et al., 2010).

50 Traditional synchronization relies on well-known closed-loop DLL/PLL architectures (Kaplan,
51 2006). However, receiver architectures based on DLL/PLL are not always able to provide continu-
52 ous and reliable phase tracking (Humphreys et al., 2005). Most of state-of-the-art (SoTA) techniques
53 propose methods to robustify DLL/PLL schemes via fine tuning and augmentation (Yu et al., 2006;
54 López-Salcedo et al., 2014), either by using adaptive bandwidth schemes (Skone et al., 2005) or
55 combined architectures (Chiou, 2010; Won, 2014). It has already been shown that Kalman filter
56 (KF)-based solutions provide better performances and robustness in these situations (Humphreys
57 et al., 2005; Macabiau et al., 2012), being nowadays the performance benchmark for the devel-
58 opment of new methodologies (Vilà-Valls et al., 2017b). The natural extension is to use adaptive
59 KF-based solutions (Zhang et al., 2010; Won et al., 2012), which aim at sequentially adapt the filter
60 parameters. However, even these advanced techniques do not solve the estimation versus mitigation
61 trade-off (Vilà-Valls et al., 2015b), because the filter is not able to decouple the different phase con-
62 tributions (i.e., dynamics and scintillation), and so may provide poor scintillation *mitigation* capa-
63 bilities. A scalar tracking approach to overcome these limitations was proposed in (Vilà-Valls et al.,
64 2015b,a), where the scintillation physical phenomena is statistically modeled using autoregressive
65 (AR) processes and embedded in the filter formulation. This approach was shown to outperform the
66 SoTA techniques using synthetic data, being effectively able to discriminate between dynamic and
67 scintillation contributions to the estimated carrier-phase. The Cornell Scintillation Model (CSM)
68 (Humphreys et al., 2009, 2010), a popular synthetic signal simulator that generates scintillation
69 amplitude and phase traces, was used to test the AR-based filtering methodology. Recent studies
70 of real equatorial and high-latitude data have shown that scintillation characteristics are frequency-
71 dependent (Carrano et al., 2012; Sokolova et al., 2015; Jiao et al., 2016). While phase disturbances
72 may be correlated, deep amplitude fades tend to occur at different times on different frequencies,
73 thus motivating the potential performance gain of using inter-frequency aiding and multi-frequency
74 architectures.

This paper exploits the statistical relationships between scintillation at different frequency bands to propose a multi-frequency carrier tracking method that virtually mitigates scintillation component. The paper extends our previous work on single-frequency carrier tracking loops under scintillation conditions (Vilà-Valls et al., 2015b,a), for which a state-space formulation and a Kalman filter (KF) was considered. Here, an augmented state-space formulation considering multiple frequencies is investigated and a tracking method proposed on the top of it. Remarkably, the resulting method is validated with real data measurements showing notable performance.

To summarize, in this article, we further explore the idea and preliminary results in (Vilà-Valls et al., 2017a) with the following four main contributions:

- i) Multivariate AR ionospheric amplitude and phase scintillation modeling, featuring a joint fitting of the multi-frequency scintillation time series. An optimal model order selection based on the Bayesian Information Criterion is used. This is discussed in Section 3.
- ii) The novel multi-frequency joint carrier phase and scintillation state-space model (SSM) formulation, that takes into account the potential correlation at different frequency bands is introduced in Section 4.
- iii) The proposed robust filter that performs state estimation on the aforementioned SSM is discussed in Section 5. The solution is based on a nonlinear, adaptive KF formulation.
- iv) As opposed to previous works where synthetic data was used, the proposed method is analyzed using real ionospheric scintillation data in Section 6.

2. Ionospheric Scintillation

Scintillation is caused by local variations in the structure of the ionospheric electron density along line-of-sight between the satellite and the receiver. The receiver observes signals that are refracted and diffracted such that the phase and amplitude of the signal exhibits large stochastic perturbations. The severity of the scintillation is traditionally quantified by two indices: an amplitude scintillation index, denoted S_4 ; and a phase scintillation index, denoted σ_ϕ . The indices are computed on a per-signal basis and indicate average intensity of the signal variations over the preceding minute. They have been used for some decades and as a result there exist rich databases of historical data for a wide range of observation points.

Unfortunately these indices offer no insight into the time-correlatedness of the instantaneous phase and amplitude of scintillation observed on multiple frequencies. A number of recent studies have provided empirical evidence that the phase scintillation exhibits a high degree of correlation between different GNSS frequencies, including L1, L2 and L5. It has been suggested that this correlation persists except in the case of strong amplitude scintillation, when deep amplitude fades occur (Sokolova et al., 2015; Carrano et al., 2012; Jiao et al., 2016). This implies that even when strong phase scintillation is observed, which is not uncommon at high latitudes, these variations in the carrier will be correlated across frequencies. When a receiver observes both amplitude and phase scintillation, then it has been observed that the phase variations are correlated depending on the scintillation intensity, but become decorrelated once deep amplitude fades begin to occur

113 (Sokolova et al., 2015). These deep amplitude fades, it has been shown, tend to be uncorrelated
 114 across frequencies (Carrano et al., 2012).

115 From a carrier tracking perspective, these two observations can be exploited to improve and
 116 bustify carrier phase tracking. Firstly, the fact that the phase variations are highly correlated implies
 117 that a centralized, or joint tracking of the carrier across multiple GNSS frequencies can improve
 118 tracking accuracy (Sokolova et al., 2015). Secondly, the fact that deep amplitude fades occur at dif-
 119 ferent times on different frequencies, implies that it is highly unlikely that a receiver will loose lock
 120 on multiple frequencies simultaneously, suggesting that it should be possible to assist one frequency
 121 with another (Sokolova et al., 2015; Carrano et al., 2012). These concepts are explored in the work
 122 presented here.

123 The experimental work presented in this manuscript, was conducted on data obtained from the
 124 Joint Research Centre (JRC) Scintillation Repository a collection of data with more than 10 hours
 125 of scintillation events recorded over Hanoi in March and April, 2015 (Curran et al., 2015b). These
 126 datasets were based on a reconfigurable quad-channel front-end, Fourtune, which had been pro-
 127 grammed to collect triple-frequency data, L1, L2 and L5, using 1-bit complex sampling at rates of
 128 5 MHz, 5 MHz, and 30 MHz, respectively (Curran et al., 2015b). The recording system was con-
 129 figured to continuously record 50-minute datasets and to post-process each using an L1 software
 130 defined receiver for the purposes of basic scintillation detection. Those datasets in which severe
 131 scintillation was identified were then archived for post-processing, and the others discarded (Curran
 132 et al., 2015a).

133 The post-processing stage employed a multi-frequency open-loop software receiver which ex-
 134 ploited precise knowledge of the receiver location, and the well-disciplined reference oscillator to
 135 generate accurate reference carrier and code local replicas (Curran et al., 2015b). Once demodu-
 136 lated to complex baseband, the correlator values corresponding to each observed GNSS signal were
 137 processed to estimate the phase and amplitude perturbations induced by ionospheric activity. Being
 138 an open-loop post-processing scheme, a batch estimation of the amplitude and phase was possible,
 139 providing highly accurate and reliable characterization (Curran et al., 2015b). From these 1 kHz es-
 140 timates of carrier phase and amplitude, traditional measures of scintillation activity were computed,
 141 such as S_4 and σ_ϕ .

142 Figure 1 shows an example of real equatorial ionospheric scintillation amplitude data for a scin-
 143 tillation event at three different GPS frequency bands on one particular satellite. This is an example
 144 of strong scintillation, exhibiting a few fades below -30 dB, and many prolonged fades below -10
 145 dB.

146 3. Multivariate AR Scintillation Signal Model

Ionospheric scintillation can be modeled as a multiplicative channel $\xi_s(t)$, with the received base-
 band signal being

$$x(t) = \xi_s(t)s(t) + w(t), \quad \xi_s(t) = \rho_s(t)e^{j\theta_s(t)} \quad (1)$$

where $\rho_s(t)$ and $\theta_s(t)$ are the ionospheric scintillation envelope and phase components, respec-
 tively; $s(t)$ is the baseband equivalent of the transmitted signal; and $w(t)$ is a random noise term
 including both thermal noise and any other disturbance. The amplitude scintillation strength is typ-
 ically described by the scintillation index S_4 , and is usually considered within three main regions

Fig. 1. An example of 100 seconds of real equatorial scintillation amplitude data for a severe scintillation event at three different GPS frequency bands.

(Humphreys et al., 2009): weak, moderate and severe,

$$S_4 = \sqrt{\frac{\mathbb{E}(\rho_s^4) - (\mathbb{E}(\rho_s^2))^2}{(\mathbb{E}(\rho_s^2))^2}}, \quad \begin{cases} S_4 \leq 0.3 & \text{(weak)} \\ 0.3 < S_4 \leq 0.6 & \text{(moderate)} \\ 0.6 < S_4 & \text{(severe)} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

It was shown in (Vilà-Valls et al., 2013, 2015b,a) for the single-frequency case that both scintillation components can be well approximated using an autoregressive (AR) process. The scalar AR scintillation model is given by

$$\rho_{s,k} = \sum_{i=1}^q \gamma_i \rho_{s,k-i} + \kappa + \eta_{\rho,k}, \quad \eta_{\rho,k} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\eta_\rho}^2), \quad (3)$$

$$\theta_{s,k} = \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i \theta_{s,k-i} + \eta_{\theta,k}, \quad \eta_{\theta,k} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\eta_\theta}^2), \quad (4)$$

147 with κ a constant value, and the mean of the amplitude scintillation process equal to $\mu = \kappa / (1 -$
 148 $\sum_{i=1}^q \gamma_i)$; $\{\gamma_i, \beta_i\}$ are the set of AR coefficients, and $\{\sigma_{\eta_\rho}^2, \sigma_{\eta_\theta}^2\}$ the driving noise variances. In (Vilà-
 149 Valls et al., 2017a), we considered this scalar AR approximation to build a multi-frequency SSM,
 150 where the model order selection and AR parameters were obtained from synthetic scintillation data.
 151 Using this scalar approximation in a multi-frequency scenario is a simplistic approach, because it
 152 does not take into account the possible correlations among frequencies, and therefore loses the char-
 153 acteristics of the physical phenomena (see Section 2). To overcome the limitations of the scalar AR
 154 processes model in this context, we propose a new multivariate AR (MAR) ionospheric scintillation
 155 formulation. Real ionospheric scintillation data was used, selecting the model order and parameters.

156

Definition 1 (MAR(p)) A multivariate AR model of order p is defined as

$$\mathbf{z}_k = \mathbf{w} + \sum_{i=1}^p \mathbf{A}_i \mathbf{z}_{k-i} + \mathbf{e}_k, \quad (5)$$

where p is the model order; $\mathbf{z}_k = [z_{k,1}, \dots, z_{k,d}]^\top$ is the k -th sample of a d -dimensional time-series; \mathbf{A}_1 to $\mathbf{A}_p \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ are the coefficient matrices of the MAR model; the random vector term $\mathbf{e}_k = [e_{k,1}, \dots, e_{k,d}]^\top$ is a zero-mean Gaussian random variable with covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_e \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$. \mathbf{e}_k is assumed uncorrelated in time (i.e., $\mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{e}_k \mathbf{e}_\ell^\top\} = \mathbf{0}$ for $k \neq \ell$), but possibly correlated among time-series (i.e., $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_e$ can contain off-diagonal elements); $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is a parameter vector of intercept terms to allow a nonzero mean time-series, which implies an expected value of

$$\bar{\mathbf{z}}_k = (\mathbf{I} - \sum_{i=1}^p \mathbf{A}_i)^{-1} \mathbf{w}. \quad (6)$$

157

158 The two main MAR modelling challenges are: i) selection the correct model order selection p ,
 159 and ii) the time-series analysis to obtain an estimate of the MAR model parameters, $\{\mathbf{w}, \{\mathbf{A}_i\}_{i=1}^p, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_e\}$.
 160 Both points are discussed in the remainder of this section.

161 3.1. MAR Model Order Selection

162 In the statistical and signal processing literature, the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) (Akaike,
 163 1974), extensions of the AIC such as the corrected AIC (AICc) and the generalized information
 164 criterion (GIC), and the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) (Schwarz, 1978), are widely used
 165 metrics for model order selection. The latter has become the method of choice mainly because: i)
 166 while the AIC has a nonzero overfitting probability, this tends to zero in the BIC when the sample
 167 size grows, and ii) it is an asymptotic approximation of the optimal maximum a posteriori (MAP)
 168 rule (Stoica and Selen, 2004). In this contribution we use the BIC as the model order selection
 169 criterion.

170 In this subsection we define the quantities for a generic time-series composed of N samples,
 171 $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^N$, and assume θ is the vector parameters of the model with order p , which we aim to select.

172

Definition 2 (BIC) The Bayesian Information Criterion is defined as (Stoica and Selen, 2004)

$$\text{BIC} = -2 \ln p_p(\mathbf{y}, \hat{\theta}) + p \ln N, \quad (7)$$

173 with \mathbf{y} being the available data, θ the parameter vector (whose dimension can vary with the model
 174 order) and p corresponds to the model order. $p_p(\mathbf{y}, \theta)$ is the likelihood function which depends on the
 175 parameter vector θ and the model order p , and the maximum likelihood estimate of the parameters
 176 is given by $\hat{\theta} = \arg \max_{\theta} \ln p_p(\mathbf{y}, \theta)$. The BIC rule selects the order p that maximizes (7).

177

178 Def. 2 corresponds to the BIC when a single time-series is fitted. We are, however, interested
 179 in jointly fitting multiple time-series (from the various frequencies). This concept is generalized in
 180 Def. 3.

181

Definition 3 (Multivariate BIC) The Bayesian Information Criterion for the multivariate AR model $\text{MAR}(p)$ in Def. 1 yields to a model order estimate according to (Neumaier and Schneider, 2001)

$$\hat{p} = \arg \min_p \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_p}{d} - \left(1 - \frac{dp + 1}{N} \right) \ln N \right) \quad (8)$$

182 where $\mathcal{L}_p = \ln \det \left((N - dp - 1) \hat{\Sigma}_e(p) \right)$ and $\hat{\Sigma}_e(p)$ is an estimate of the noise covariance matrix
 183 obtained from the N samples.

184

185 The estimates of the noise covariance matrix $\hat{\Sigma}_e(p)$ are typically obtained for a range of model
 186 order values, $p_{\min} \leq p \leq p_{\max}$. An efficient iterative way to compute an estimate of \mathcal{L}_p using a QR
 187 factorization and a stepwise downdating strategy is shown in (Neumaier and Schneider, 2001).

188 3.2. MAR Model Parameters

189 Several MAR model parameters estimation methods based on the minimization of the prediction
 190 error are available in the literature. A thorough comparison of the most common estimators is
 191 available in (Schlögl, 2006). The main conclusion is that when enough samples are available (i.e.,
 192 $N \geq 400$), the performance of the different methods is similar. In this contribution we propose to use
 193 the stepwise least squares estimation method proposed in (Neumaier and Schneider, 2001), which
 194 is available as a MatlabTM package named ARfit (Schneider and Neumaier, 2001). This method
 195 first rewrites the MAR model as a regression model, and then obtains the parameters using a least
 196 squares method.

197 3.3. Ionospheric Scintillation MAR Formulation

The MAR multi-frequency ionospheric scintillation model considering M frequency bands (i.e., B_1 to B_M) is given by

$$\rho_{s,k} = \sum_{i=1}^q \Gamma_i \rho_{s,k-i} + \kappa + \mathbf{e}_{\rho,k}, \quad \mathbf{e}_{\rho,k} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \Sigma_\rho), \quad (9)$$

$$\theta_{s,k} = \sum_{i=1}^p \Delta_i \theta_{s,k-i} + \mathbf{e}_{\theta,k}, \quad \mathbf{e}_{\theta,k} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \Sigma_\theta), \quad (10)$$

198 where $\rho_{s,k} = [\rho_{s,k}^{B_1}, \dots, \rho_{s,k}^{B_M}]^\top$, $\theta_{s,k} = [\theta_{s,k}^{B_1}, \dots, \theta_{s,k}^{B_M}]^\top$, and the ensemble of $q + p + 3$ MAR model
 199 parameters is given by $[\{\Gamma_i\}_{i=1}^q, \kappa, \{\Delta_i\}_{i=1}^p, \Sigma_\rho, \Sigma_\theta]$. Notice that each of these matrices has dimension
 200 $M \times M$, given by the number of frequency bands. It is worth saying that the MAR model noise
 201 covariance matrices, Σ_ρ and Σ_θ , provide a good indicator of the inter-frequency correlation of the
 202 time-series. It has been found empirically from the estimated noise covariances that while Σ_ρ is
 203 almost diagonal (i.e., no correlation in the ionospheric scintillation amplitude), significant values
 204 off the main diagonal appear in Σ_θ (i.e., higher inter-frequency correlation in the ionospheric scin-
 205 tillation phase).

206 A key point to exploit the MAR scintillation approximation within a filtering framework is the
 207 model order selection. In (Vilà-Valls et al., 2013, 2015b,a), the selection was done inspecting the

power spectral densities (PSD), and subsequently in (Vilà-Valls et al., 2017a), we used a statistical test based on the partial autocorrelation functions (PAF). Both analysis were done using synthetic data. In this contribution we use the BIC in Def. 3 and perform the fitting on real multi-frequency scintillation data.

Figure 2 shows the C/N_0 (carrier-to-noise density ratio) and amplitude scintillation index estimations, S_4 , at three different GPS frequency bands (i.e., L1, L2, and L5). These results correspond to two ionospheric scintillation events recorded over Hanoi in March and April 2015 (cf. Section 2). While the first event (top figure) corresponds to a moderate to low scintillation scenario, the second one (bottom figure) is clearly a strong scintillation case. Thus, the real data available (over 3 hours of equatorial scintillation) contains both low, moderate and severe scintillation scenarios.

To obtain the model order for both amplitude and phase scintillation processes, we processed over 4 hours of 3-dimensional time-series to compute the BIC metrics in (8). BIC results are obtained from non-overlapped sequences of $N = 500$ samples (5 seconds). In contrast to the single-frequency fitting to synthetic data given in (Vilà-Valls et al., 2013, 2015b,a), the conclusion from the MAR analysis is that a suitable model order to fit the majority of scintillation scenarios is given by $q = 6$ and $p = 5$, i.e. a MAR(6) and MAR(5) for the scintillation amplitude and phase, respectively. These results are in contrast to the analysis of previous contributions (based on synthetic data), where lower orders were sufficient. To justify the choice of the model order, we plot in Figure 3 the histograms of the order selection obtained from real multi-frequency ionospheric scintillation data.

4. Multi-frequency GNSS and Ionospheric Scintillation State-Space Model

4.1. Single Frequency GNSS Signal Model

The generic GNSS baseband transmitted signal is given by

$$s(t) = \sqrt{2P_x(t)}d(t - \tau(t))c(t - \tau(t))e^{j\theta(t)}, \quad (11)$$

with $P_x(t)$ the received power, $d(t)$ the navigation message and $c(t)$ the spreading code, $\tau(t)$ the code delay and $\theta(t) = 2\pi f_d(t) + \theta_e(t)$ the carrier phase, where $f_d(t)$ is the carrier Doppler frequency shift and $\theta_e(t)$ a carrier phase term including other phase impairments. After the acquisition stage, the samples at the output of the correlators are (Spilker, 1996)

$$y_k = A_k d_k R(\Delta\tau_k) \frac{\sin(\pi\Delta f_{d,k} T_s)}{\pi\Delta f_{d,k} T_s} e^{j(2\pi\Delta f_{d,k} T_s + \Delta\theta_k)} + n_k,$$

where T_s is the the sampling rate, k stands for the discrete time $t_k = kT_s$, A_k is the signal amplitude at the output of the correlators, d_k is the data bit, $R(\cdot)$ is the code autocorrelation function and $\{\Delta\tau_k, \Delta f_{d,k}, \Delta\theta_k\}$ are, respectively, the code delay, Doppler shift and carrier phase errors. Focusing on carrier-tracking, we work under the assumption of perfect timing synchronization and data wipe-off, resulting in a signal model

$$y_k = \alpha_k e^{j\theta_k} + n_k, \quad n_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{n,k}^2), \quad (12)$$

where amplitude α_k and phase θ_k may include any non-nominal harsh propagation disturbance. For instance, including the ionospheric scintillation into the signal model leads to $\alpha_k = A_k \rho_{s,k}$ and

Fig. 2. C/N_0 and S_4 scintillation index estimation at three GPS frequency bands for two ionospheric scintillation events recorded over Hanoi in March and April 2015.

231 $\theta_k = \theta_{d,k} + \theta_{s,k}$. The dynamics phase term $\theta_{d,k}$ refers to the line-of-sight (LOS) phase evolution due
 232 to the relative movement between the satellite and the receiver.

Standard carrier tracking architectures, being proportional plus integral controller in the form of a PLL, model $\theta_{d,k}$ using a Taylor approximation of the time-varying phase evolution according to the expected dynamics. Typically, a 3rd order representation of the dynamics phase evolution is considered

$$\theta_{d,k} = \theta_0 + 2\pi(f_{d,k}kT_s + f_{r,k}k^2T_s^2/2), \quad (13)$$

Fig. 3. Empirical model order probability density functions obtained from real multi-frequency ionospheric scintillation data.

233 where θ_0 (rad) is a random phase value, $f_{d,k}$ (Hz) the carrier Doppler frequency, and $f_{r,k}$ (Hz/s) the
 234 Doppler frequency rate.

235 4.2. Multi-frequency GNSS State-Space Model

In a multi-frequency architecture, a single satellite transmits simultaneously at different frequencies, therefore at the receiver side several measurements are available. Although the methodology in this paper is general for any GNSS signal, we focus on a modern GPS triple band satellite, which transmits on the L_1 , L_2 and L_5 frequencies. In this case, the measurements are given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} y_k^{L_1} \\ y_k^{L_2} \\ y_k^{L_5} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_k^{L_1} e^{j(\theta_{d,k}^{L_1} + \theta_{s,k}^{L_1})} \\ \alpha_k^{L_2} e^{j(\theta_{d,k}^{L_2} + \theta_{s,k}^{L_2})} \\ \alpha_k^{L_5} e^{j(\theta_{d,k}^{L_5} + \theta_{s,k}^{L_5})} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} n_k^{L_1} \\ n_k^{L_2} \\ n_k^{L_5} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

which may be useful to rewrite in real form as

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} y_{i,k}^{L_1} \\ y_{q,k}^{L_1} \\ y_{i,k}^{L_2} \\ y_{q,k}^{L_2} \\ y_{i,k}^{L_5} \\ y_{q,k}^{L_5} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{y}_k} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \alpha_k^{L_1} \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_k^{L_1}) \\ \sin(\theta_k^{L_1}) \end{bmatrix} \\ \alpha_k^{L_2} \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_k^{L_2}) \\ \sin(\theta_k^{L_2}) \end{bmatrix} \\ \alpha_k^{L_5} \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_k^{L_5}) \\ \sin(\theta_k^{L_5}) \end{bmatrix} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}_k)} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} n_{i,k}^{L_1} \\ n_{q,k}^{L_1} \\ n_{i,k}^{L_2} \\ n_{q,k}^{L_2} \\ n_{i,k}^{L_5} \\ n_{q,k}^{L_5} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{n}_k}, \quad (15)$$

236 where for each frequency, $y_k = y_{i,k} + iy_{q,k}$, $\theta_k = \theta_{d,k} + \theta_{s,k}$ and $n_k = n_{i,k} + jn_{q,k}$.

The different LOS carrier-phase evolutions, when referencing all of the dynamics to L_1 , are given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \theta_{d,k}^{L_1} \\ \theta_{d,k}^{L_2} \\ \theta_{d,k}^{L_5} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_0^{L_1} + 2\pi(f_{d,k}kT_s + f_{r,k}k^2T_s^2/2) \\ \theta_0^{L_2} + 2\pi f_{L_2}/f_{L_1}(f_{d,k}kT_s + f_{r,k}k^2T_s^2/2) \\ \theta_0^{L_5} + 2\pi f_{L_5}/f_{L_1}(f_{d,k}kT_s + f_{r,k}k^2T_s^2/2) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (16)$$

with f_{L_1} , f_{L_2} and f_{L_5} being the carrier frequencies at the different bands. It is important to notice that the same Doppler frequency terms, $f_{d,k}$ and $f_{r,k}$, appear in both frequencies. The multi-frequency noise diagonal covariance matrix is

$$\mathbf{R}_k = \text{diag}(\sigma_{n_{L_1,k}}^2, \sigma_{n_{L_1,k}}^2, \sigma_{n_{L_2,k}}^2, \sigma_{n_{L_2,k}}^2, \sigma_{n_{L_5,k}}^2, \sigma_{n_{L_5,k}}^2)/2.$$

In general, \mathbf{x}_k refers to the state to be tracked and is defined as $\mathbf{x}_k \doteq [\mathbf{x}_{d,k}^\top, \mathbf{x}_{\rho,k}^\top, \mathbf{x}_{\theta,k}^\top]^\top$ with dimension $n_x = 5 + 3q + 3p$ and

$$\mathbf{x}_{d,k} \doteq [\theta_{d,k}^{L_1}, \theta_{d,k}^{L_2}, \theta_{d,k}^{L_5}, f_{d,k}, f_{r,k}]^\top, \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{\rho,k} \doteq [\boldsymbol{\rho}_{s,k}^\top, \boldsymbol{\rho}_{s,k-1}^\top, \dots, \boldsymbol{\rho}_{s,k-q+1}^\top]^\top, \quad (18)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{\theta,k} \doteq [\boldsymbol{\theta}_{s,k}^\top, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{s,k-1}^\top, \dots, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{s,k-p+1}^\top]^\top. \quad (19)$$

The LOS dynamic carrier-phase state evolution

$$\mathbf{x}_{d,k} = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 2\pi T_s & \pi T_s^2 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 2\pi \delta_{L_2} T_s & \pi \delta_{L_2} T_s^2 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 2\pi \delta_{L_5} T_s & \pi \delta_{L_5} T_s^2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & T_s \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}}_{\mathbf{F}_d} \mathbf{x}_{d,k-1} + \mathbf{v}_{d,k}, \quad (20)$$

237 where $\delta_{L_2} = f_{L_2}/f_{L_1}$, $\delta_{L_5} = f_{L_5}/f_{L_1}$ and $\mathbf{v}_{d,k} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{Q}_{d,k})$ stands for possible uncertainties or mis-
 238 matches on the dynamic model. The covariance $\mathbf{Q}_{d,k}$ is usually *a priori* fixed according to the
 239 problem under consideration.

From the MAR scintillation model in (9), the multi-frequency scintillation amplitude state evolution is

$$\mathbf{x}_{\rho,k} = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{\Gamma}_1 & \dots & \mathbf{\Gamma}_{q-1} & \mathbf{\Gamma}_q \\ \mathbf{I}_M & & & \\ & \ddots & & \\ & & \mathbf{I}_M & \end{pmatrix}}_{\mathbf{F}_\rho} \mathbf{x}_{\rho,k-1} + \boldsymbol{\kappa}_\rho + \mathbf{v}_{\rho,k}, \quad (21)$$

where the elements not specified are 0, \mathbf{I}_M refers to the identity matrix of dimension $M \times M$, $\mathbf{v}_{\rho,k} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{Q}_{\rho,k})$ with block diagonal covariance matrix $\mathbf{Q}_{\rho,k} = \text{blkdiag}(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\rho, \mathbf{0}_{M(q-1) \times M(q-1)})$ and $\boldsymbol{\kappa}_\rho$ is a null vector except for the first M values given by $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$. Equivalently, we define the scintillation phase state

evolution from (10) as

$$\mathbf{x}_{\theta,k} = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} \Delta_1 & \cdots & \Delta_{p-1} & \Delta_p \\ \mathbf{I}_M & & & \\ & \ddots & & \\ & & & \mathbf{I}_M \end{pmatrix}}_{\mathbf{F}_\theta} \mathbf{x}_{\rho,k-1} + \mathbf{v}_{\theta,k}, \quad (22)$$

with $\mathbf{v}_{\theta,k} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{Q}_{\theta,k})$ and block diagonal covariance matrix $\mathbf{Q}_{\theta,k} = \text{blkdiag}(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\theta, \mathbf{0}_{M(p-1) \times M(p-1)})$. Finally, the complete state evolution equation reads,

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \underbrace{\text{diag}(\mathbf{F}_d, \mathbf{F}_\rho, \mathbf{F}_\theta)}_{\mathbf{F}_k} \mathbf{x}_{k-1} + \boldsymbol{\kappa}_T + \mathbf{v}_k, \quad (23)$$

240 where the Gaussian process noise has a block diagonal covariance matrix $\mathbf{Q}_k =$
 241 $\text{blkdiag}(\mathbf{Q}_{d,k}, \mathbf{Q}_{\rho,k}, \mathbf{Q}_{\theta,k})$. Equations (15) and (23) define the new SSM formulation. Notice that in
 242 contrast to the SSM in (Vilà-Valls et al., 2017a), in this case the possible correlation between scin-
 243 tillation amplitude and phase at different frequency bands is accounted for.

244 5. New robust filtering methodology

In this article we elaborate on the previous KF-based architecture proposed in (Vilà-Valls et al., 2017a), and extended in Section 4, where the scintillation physical phenomena is mathematically modeled and embedded into the state-space formulation. A nonlinear extended KF (EKF) formulation allows to directly operate with the received signal samples, avoiding the problems associated to the use of a phase discriminator, that is, nonlinearities, loss of Gaussianity and possible saturation at low C/N_0 . Using the SSM in (15) and (23), and the MAR formulation in Section 3.3, recall that the main parameters of the filter are

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_k(\Psi) &= \text{diag}(\mathbf{F}_d, \mathbf{F}_\rho(\{\Gamma_i\}_{i=1}^6), \mathbf{F}_\theta(\{\Delta_i\}_{i=1}^p)) \\ \mathbf{Q}_k &= \text{blkdiag}(\mathbf{Q}_{d,k}, \mathbf{Q}_{\rho,k}(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\rho), \mathbf{Q}_{\theta,k}(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\theta)), \\ \mathbf{R}_k &= \text{diag}(\sigma_{n_{L1,k}}^2, \sigma_{n_{L1,k}}^2, \sigma_{n_{L2,k}}^2, \sigma_{n_{L2,k}}^2, \sigma_{n_{L5,k}}^2, \sigma_{n_{L5,k}}^2)/2, \end{aligned}$$

245 which mainly depend on the amplitude MAR(6) and phase MAR(5) set of parameters obtained
 246 from fitting to real multi-frequency data, $\Psi = [\{\Gamma_i\}_{i=1}^6, \boldsymbol{\kappa}_T, \{\Delta_i\}_{i=1}^5, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\rho, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\theta]$. The complete state \mathbf{x}_k
 247 ($n_x = 38$) to be tracked is defined in equation (25), $\mathbf{Q}_{d,k}$ is *a priori* fixed by the user from the expected
 248 dynamics, and the measurement noise variances (i.e., $\sigma_{n_{L1,k}}^2$, $\sigma_{n_{L2,k}}^2$ and $\sigma_{n_{L5,k}}^2$) can be sequentially
 249 adjusted from the nominal C/N_0 estimators at each frequency band, being available at the receiver.

The main idea behind the EKF is to linearize the nonlinear measurement function around the predicted state estimate, and then use the standard linear KF equations (Anderson and Moore, 1979). In this case, the measurement function is given by

$$\mathbf{h}_k(\mathbf{x}_k) = \begin{bmatrix} A_k^{L_1} \rho_{s,k}^{L_1} \cos(\theta_{d,k}^{L_1} + \theta_{s,k}^{L_1}) \\ A_k^{L_1} \rho_{s,k}^{L_1} \sin(\theta_{d,k}^{L_1} + \theta_{s,k}^{L_1}) \\ A_k^{L_2} \rho_{s,k}^{L_2} \cos(\theta_{d,k}^{L_2} + \theta_{s,k}^{L_2}) \\ A_k^{L_2} \rho_{s,k}^{L_2} \sin(\theta_{d,k}^{L_2} + \theta_{s,k}^{L_2}) \\ A_k^{L_5} \rho_{s,k}^{L_5} \cos(\theta_{d,k}^{L_5} + \theta_{s,k}^{L_5}) \\ A_k^{L_5} \rho_{s,k}^{L_5} \sin(\theta_{d,k}^{L_5} + \theta_{s,k}^{L_5}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (24)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_k \doteq \left[\theta_{d,k}^{L_1}, \theta_{d,k}^{L_2}, \theta_{d,k}^{L_5}, f_{d,k}, f_{r,k}, \rho_{s,k}^{L_1}, \rho_{s,k}^{L_2}, \rho_{s,k}^{L_5}, \dots, \rho_{s,k-5}^{L_1}, \rho_{s,k-5}^{L_2}, \rho_{s,k-5}^{L_5}, \theta_{s,k}^{L_1}, \theta_{s,k}^{L_2}, \theta_{s,k}^{L_5}, \dots, \theta_{s,k-4}^{L_1}, \theta_{s,k-4}^{L_2}, \theta_{s,k-4}^{L_5} \right]^T \quad (25)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{d,k} = \begin{bmatrix} -A_k^{L_1} \hat{\rho}_{s,k|k-1}^{L_1} \sin(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_1}) & 0 & 0 \\ A_k^{L_1} \hat{\rho}_{s,k|k-1}^{L_1} \cos(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_1}) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -A_k^{L_2} \hat{\rho}_{s,k|k-1}^{L_2} \sin(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_2}) & 0 \\ 0 & A_k^{L_2} \hat{\rho}_{s,k|k-1}^{L_2} \cos(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_2}) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -A_k^{L_5} \hat{\rho}_{s,k|k-1}^{L_5} \sin(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_5}) \\ 0 & 0 & A_k^{L_5} \hat{\rho}_{s,k|k-1}^{L_5} \cos(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_5}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (26)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{\rho,k} = \begin{bmatrix} A_k^{L_1} \cos(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_1}) & 0 & 0 \\ A_k^{L_1} \sin(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_1}) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & A_k^{L_2} \cos(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_2}) & 0 \\ 0 & A_k^{L_2} \sin(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_2}) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & A_k^{L_5} \cos(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_5}) \\ 0 & 0 & A_k^{L_5} \sin(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_5}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (27)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{\theta,k} = \begin{bmatrix} -A_k^{L_1} \hat{\rho}_{s,k|k-1}^{L_1} \sin(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_1}) & 0 & 0 \\ A_k^{L_1} \hat{\rho}_{s,k|k-1}^{L_1} \cos(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_1}) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -A_k^{L_2} \hat{\rho}_{s,k|k-1}^{L_2} \sin(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_2}) & 0 \\ 0 & A_k^{L_2} \hat{\rho}_{s,k|k-1}^{L_2} \cos(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_2}) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -A_k^{L_5} \hat{\rho}_{s,k|k-1}^{L_5} \sin(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_5}) \\ 0 & 0 & A_k^{L_5} \hat{\rho}_{s,k|k-1}^{L_5} \cos(\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_5}) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (28)$$

and the linearized (Jacobian) measurement matrix to be used in the KF measurement update step is¹

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_k = \nabla \mathbf{h}_k(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1}) = \left[\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{d,k}, \mathbf{0}_{6 \times 2}, \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{\rho,k}, \mathbf{0}_{6 \times 15}, \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{\theta,k}, \mathbf{0}_{6 \times 12} \right]$$

with the different matrices given in equations (26)-(28). Note that the matrix is evaluated at the predicted state, $\mathbf{x}_k = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1}$, with $\hat{\theta}_{k|k-1}^{L_j} \doteq \hat{\theta}_{d,k|k-1}^{L_j} + \hat{\theta}_{s,k|k-1}^{L_j}$ for each frequency².

For the sake of completeness, the EKF formulation of the general carrier-phase tracking problem is sketched in Algorithm 1. Notice that the Kalman gain, \mathbf{K}_k , is computed from the possibly time-varying system noise matrices, \mathbf{Q}_k and \mathbf{R}_k , which implies that the filter is adapting its behavior to the actual working conditions and has an implicit adaptive bandwidth, in contrast to the traditional PLL with constant coefficients (i.e., fixed bandwidth) (Vilà-Valls et al., 2017b).

In practice, we compute an estimate of the MAR parameters using a subset of the real multi-frequency ionospheric scintillation data available. To obtain meaningful results, in the simulations we use a small sample set to obtain the model parameters and process the rest of the scintillation

¹ The vector differential operator is defined as $\nabla = \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1}, \dots, \frac{\partial}{\partial x_N} \right]$.

² $_{k|k-1}$ refers to the predicted estimate at time k using measurements up to time $k-1$, and $_{k|k}$ refers to the estimated value at time k using measurements up to time k .

Event	Low Scint	Moderate Scint	Severe Scint
# 1	t=1500-2500s	t=100-1500s	
# 2	t=100-1800s		
# 3	t=100-1700s		t=1700-2800s
# 4		t=700-2000s	t=100-700, 2000-2500s
# 5	t=100-2900s		
# 6		t=700-950s, 1300-1700s	t=100-700, 950-1300, 1700-2900s

Table 1. Real Equatorial Multi-frequency Ionospheric Scintillation Data Characterization

270 The different events are described in Table 1, with the corresponding estimation of the scintillation
 271 index S_4 shown in Figure 5. From the state vector in (25), the parameters of interest are the phase
 272 components related to the dynamics of the receiver, i.e., obtaining a good estimate of these param-
 273 eters directly implies good ionospheric scintillation mitigation capabilities. Therefore, this is the
 274 final goal of the new receiver architecture. Note that in some applications it may be interesting to
 275 obtain an estimate of the scintillation amplitude and phase components, $\rho_{s,k}$ and $\theta_{s,k}$.

276 The results obtained with the MAR-EKF are compared to the current state-of-the-art techniques,
 277 and the latest contributions using scalar AR scintillation model approximations:

- 278 i) 3rd order PLL with equivalent bandwidth $B_w = 5$ Hz.
- 279 ii) Standard discriminator-based KF-based tracking.
- 280 iii) Adaptive discriminator-based KF (AKF), adjusting the measurement noise variance from the
 281 C/N_0 estimate.
- 282 iv) The scalar AKF-AR presented in (Vilà-Valls et al., 2015b), only tracking the scintillation phase,
 283 and using a C/N_0 estimate to tune the measurement noise variance at the output of the discrimi-
 284 nator.
- 285 v) The scalar AEKF-AR presented in (Vilà-Valls et al., 2015a), tracking both scintillation amplitude
 286 and phase, treating each frequency separately.

We consider a Doppler profile given by an initial random phase in $[-\pi, \pi]$, initial Doppler $f_{d,0} =$
 50 Hz and rate $f_{r,0} = 100$ Hz/s, and a relatively low nominal $C/N_0 = 30$ dB-Hz. The signal is
 sampled at $T_s = 10$ ms. The measure of performance is the root mean square error (RMSE) on the
 carrier-phase of interest, i.e., $\theta_{d,k}^{L_1}$, $\theta_{d,k}^{L_2}$ and $\theta_{d,k}^{L_5}$. We define the RMSE (radians) over time for each
 frequency L_j as

$$\text{RMSE}_t(L_j) = \frac{1}{N_t} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{N_t} (\theta_{d,i}^{L_j} - \hat{\theta}_{d,i}^{L_j})^2}, \quad (29)$$

287 which is obtained from long real data sets of N_t samples.

288 The proposed methodology is characterized via an in depth analysis, considering the steady-state
 289 performance for several representative scenarios: i) a low scintillation scenario which is used as an
 290 architecture validation, ii) scintillation mitigation capabilities in challenging moderate and severe

Fig. 5. Estimated scintillation index S_4 for the 6 sets of real multi-frequency equatorial scintillation data, i.e., #1 (top) to #6 (bottom).

291 scintillation scenarios, iii) robustness to modeling mismatch, where we take into account possi-
 292 ble scintillation under and overestimation, and iv) the estimation performance for the ionospheric
 293 scintillation amplitude and phase components.

Event #3	RMSE _t (L ₁)	RMSE _t (L ₂)	RMSE _t (L ₅)
PLL	0.0804	0.0772	0.0767
KF	0.0465	0.0419	0.0392
AKF	0.0465	0.0421	0.0392
AKF-AR	0.0451	0.0408	0.0373
AEKF-AR	0.0116	0.0122	0.0116
MAR-EKF	0.0093	0.0092	0.0069
Event #2	RMSE _t (L ₁)	RMSE _t (L ₂)	RMSE _t (L ₅)
PLL	0.1476	0.0812	0.0766
KF	0.1248	0.0484	0.0473
AKF	0.1245	0.0481	0.0473
AKF-AR	0.1229	0.0467	0.0465
AEKF-AR	0.0699	0.0113	0.0121
MAR-EKF	0.0093	0.0100	0.0107

Table 2. Root mean square phase tracking error considering real scintillation data at different GPS frequency bands for the low scintillation events #3 ($t = 200 - 700s$) and #2 ($t = 200 - 700s$)

294 6.1. Low Scintillation Scenario: Architecture Validation

295 In general, it is held that low ionospheric scintillation conditions are given for $S_4 < 0.4$. From
 296 Figure 5, we easily identify these conditions in the scintillation events #1 ($t = 1500 - 2500s$), #2
 297 ($t = 100 - 1800s$), #3 ($t = 100 - 1700s$) and #5 ($t = 100 - 1900s$). A desired behavior of any tracking
 298 method designed to mitigate moderate and severe scintillation conditions is that it performs at least
 299 as good as the standard tracking techniques when low or no scintillation is present. Therefore,
 300 analyzing the performance of the proposed MAR-EKF in such scenarios can be understood as a
 301 representative architecture validation procedure.

302 We show the RMSE_t(L_j) in radians, obtained for two different low scintillation scenarios (500s of
 303 data), in Table 2. In this case, we can see that the performance obtained with the two EKF-based so-
 304 lutions, i.e., AEKF-AR and MAR-EKF, is similar but slightly better with the MAR-EKF. Moreover,
 305 these methods provide a lower RMSE than the one given by the PLL and the three discriminator-
 306 based KF solutions, i.e., KF, AKF and AKF-AR. Therefore, we have two main conclusions: *i*) the
 307 proposed architecture is a valid approach even if no scintillation is present in the signal, that is,
 308 the filter is robust and including the scintillation components into the state to be tracked does not
 309 induce an error on the estimation of the dynamics related phase, and *ii*) it may be preferable to avoid
 310 discriminator-based architectures and operate directly with the received signal samples. Moreover,
 311 in this case we can include the scintillation amplitude into the state formulation, thus being aware
 312 of possible fading and amplitude variations.

313 6.2. Assessing the Scintillation Mitigation Capabilities in Moderate and Severe Scintillation 314 Scenarios

315 The main goal of the proposed architecture is to effectively counteract the undesired ionospheric
 316 effects in moderate and severe scintillation scenarios, without sacrificing performance in nominal

317 scenarios (cf. Section 6.1). In this section, we analyze the performance of the MAR-EKF under
 318 harsh propagation conditions as per Table 1.

319 6.2.1. Moderate Scintillation

320 For the sake of completeness, we plot an example of the steady-state instantaneous dynamics phase
 321 estimation error for the moderate scintillation event #1 ($t=200-600s$) at L5, obtained with the AKF-
 322 AR, AEKF-AR and the MAR-EKF. Notice that we do not plot the results for the other methods
 323 because their performance is significantly poorer (see Table 3 for RMSE results). In view of the
 324 results, the benefits of the new multi-frequency approach with respect to the other filters using
 325 scalar AR approximations are apparent.

Fig. 6. Steady-state instantaneous dynamics phase estimation error for the moderate scintillation event #1 ($t=200-600s$) at L5.

326 To obtain statistically more representative results, we show the $RMSE_t(L_j)$, obtained for events
 327 #1 ($t = 500 - 1000s$) and #4 ($t = 1300 - 1800s$), in Table 3. These results verify the appropriate
 328 behavior of the new architecture, indicating that it outperforms the other methods methods under
 329 moderate scintillation conditions. Again, there is a significant performance improvement attained
 330 when avoiding the use of a discriminator. Specifically, the performance obtained with the AEKF-
 331 AR and MAR-EKF is improved with respect to the other methods. This is due to the Gaussianity
 332 assumption, which is does not hold when working with a discriminator under fading conditions
 333 (Vilà-Valls et al., 2017b).

334 6.2.2. Severe Scintillation

335 Finally, we assess the performance of the MAR-EKF in challenging, severe scintillation conditions.
 336 Figure 7 shows an example of the steady-state instantaneous dynamics phase estimation error for

Event #1	$RMSE_t(L_1)$	$RMSE_t(L_2)$	$RMSE_t(L_5)$
PLL	0.0886	0.1304	0.1490
KF	0.0915	0.1588	0.1719
AKF	0.0899	0.1521	0.1632
AKF-AR	0.0684	0.1029	0.1504
AEKF-AR	0.0466	0.0865	0.7530
MAR-EKF	0.0400	0.0301	0.0255
Event #4	$RMSE_t(L_1)$	$RMSE_t(L_2)$	$RMSE_t(L_5)$
PLL	0.0988	0.1267	0.1299
KF	0.0956	0.1418	0.1450
AKF	0.0944	0.1396	0.1448
AKF-AR	0.1002	0.1480	0.1500
AEKF-AR	0.0156	0.0228	0.0247
MAR-EKF	0.0153	0.0127	0.0129

Table 3. Root mean square phase tracking error considering real scintillation data at different GPS frequency bands for the moderate scintillation events #1 ($t = 500-1000s$) and #4 ($t = 1300-1800s$)

337 the severe scintillation event #6 ($t=1800-2200s$) at L2, obtained with the AKF-AR, AEKF-AR and
 338 the MAR-EKF. The best estimation performance is given by the MAR-EKF.

Fig. 7. Steady-state instantaneous dynamics phase estimation error for the severe scintillation event #6 ($t=1800-2200s$) at L2.

339 The $RMSE_t(L_j)$, obtained for events #3 ($t = 2000 - 2500s$), #4 ($t = 2000 - 2500s$) and #6
 340 ($t = 1700 - 2200s$), is shown in Table 4. These results confirm that the new architecture is superior
 341 to the rest of tracking methods also under severe scintillation, providing a significant performance

Event #3	RMSE _t (L ₁)	RMSE _t (L ₂)	RMSE _t (L ₅)
PLL	0.5400	0.6568	0.6928
KF	0.6400	0.7740	0.8122
AKF	0.6540	0.8269	0.8850
AKF-AR	0.4936	0.4879	0.5394
AEKF-AR	0.3310	0.2671	0.2537
MAR-EKF	0.1774	0.1567	0.1698
Event #4	RMSE _t (L ₁)	RMSE _t (L ₂)	RMSE _t (L ₅)
PLL	0.1527	0.2324	0.2330
KF	0.1742	0.2835	0.2888
AKF	0.1725	0.2765	0.2784
AKF-AR	0.1835	0.2221	0.1806
AEKF-AR	0.0374	0.0467	0.0445
MAR-EKF	0.0341	0.0284	0.0283
Event #6	RMSE _t (L ₁)	RMSE _t (L ₂)	RMSE _t (L ₅)
PLL	0.7083	0.8431	0.8805
KF	0.8468	1.0048	1.0497
AKF	0.8812	1.0502	1.1056
AKF-AR	0.5556	0.7893	0.7826
AEKF-AR	0.2707	0.5290	0.4254
MAR-EKF	0.2344	0.2087	0.2007

Table 4. Root mean square phase tracking error considering real scintillation data at different GPS frequency bands for the strong scintillation events #3 ($t = 2000 - 2500s$), #4 ($t = 2000 - 2500s$) and #6 ($t = 1700 - 2200s$).

342 improvement with respect to standard approaches and the scalar EKF-based solution in (Vilà-Valls
343 et al., 2015a), which justifies the interest and importance of considering a multi-frequency approach.
344 Overall, the MAR-EKF appears to be relatively robust against a wide range scintillation propagation
345 conditions.

346 6.3. Robustness to Modeling Mismatch

347 To fully characterize the proposed methodology, we analyze the impact of an incorrect MAR model
348 parameters estimation on the filter performance, that is, fitting the scintillation amplitude MAR(6)
349 and phase MAR(5) to a set of real data with a different scintillation behavior than the actual signal
350 being processed. Two cases are considered: i) underestimation of the scintillation conditions, which
351 implies that while the filter deals with a severe scintillation scenario, the MAR model parameters
352 are fitted to moderate scintillation data; and ii) overestimation of the scintillation conditions, which
353 refers to the moderate scintillation case with MAR model parameters fitted to severe scintillation
354 data.

355 The RMSE_t(L_j), obtained for the severe scintillation event #6 ($t = 1700 - 2200s$) considering an
356 underestimated fitting, and for the moderate scintillation event #6 ($t = 1300 - 1700s$) with an over-

Event #6 Severe	RMSE _t (L ₁)	RMSE _t (L ₂)	RMSE _t (L ₅)
MAR-EKF under	0.3922	0.3196	0.3248
MAR-EKF correct	0.2344	0.2087	0.2007
Event #6 Moderate	RMSE _t (L ₁)	RMSE _t (L ₂)	RMSE _t (L ₅)
MAR-EKF over	0.1118	0.1128	0.1341
MAR-EKF correct	0.0894	0.0701	0.0681

Table 5. Root mean square phase tracking error considering real scintillation data under modeling mismatch for the severe scintillation event #6 ($t = 1700 - 2200s$) and the moderate scintillation event #6 ($t = 1300 - 1700s$).

357 estimated fitting, is shown in Table 5. It is interesting to note that the performance degradation when
 358 having a model mismatch is reasonably bounded. In practice, it is always desirable to overestimate,
 359 rather than underestimate, the scintillation intensity.

360 6.4. Scintillation Amplitude and Phase Estimation

In this section we analyze the estimation performance for the scintillation amplitude and phase components, $\rho_{s,k}$ and $\theta_{s,k}$. We define the corresponding RMSE over time for each frequency L_j as

$$\text{RMSE}_t(\rho_{s,L_j}) = \frac{1}{N_t} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{N_t} (\rho_{s,i}^{L_j} - \hat{\rho}_{s,i}^{L_j})^2}, \quad (30)$$

$$\text{RMSE}_t(\theta_{s,L_j}) = \frac{1}{N_t} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{N_t} (\theta_{s,i}^{L_j} - \hat{\theta}_{s,i}^{L_j})^2}, \quad (31)$$

361 which are obtained from N_t data samples. Notice that standard methods track the complete phase
 362 of the signal, therefore we do not have an estimate of the scintillation components. The results
 363 obtained with the MAR-EKF are compared to the scalar AKF-AR (i.e, only scintillation phase) and
 364 AEKF-AR.

365 First we plot an example of the scintillation amplitude and phase estimates delivered by the
 366 MAR-EKF, for the severe scintillation event #3 at L5, in Figure 8. We can observe a remarkable
 367 recovery of scintillation components by the MAR-EKF filter. Both RMSE_t(ρ_{s,L_j}) and RMSE_t(θ_{s,L_j})
 368 are shown in Table 6. Again, we confirm that the MAR-EKF provides the best estimation perfor-
 369 mance for both scintillation amplitude and phase components. The performance gain with respect
 370 to the other methods using scalar AR approximations is clear for the severe scintillation scenario. In
 371 the moderate scintillation case, the performance obtained with the AEKF-AR and the MAR-EKF
 372 are equivalent.

373 6.5. Cycle Slip Performance Analysis

374 To conclude the characterization of the new methodology, we assess its robustness to cycle slips,
 375 which is particularly necessary in carrier-based positioning techniques such as real-time-kinematic
 376 (RTK) and precise-point-positioning (PPP) that rely on the integrity of carrier phase measurements.

Fig. 8. Scintillation amplitude and phase estimation for the severe scintillation event #3 at L5.

Event #1	$RMSE_t(\rho_{s,L_1})$	$RMSE_t(\rho_{s,L_2})$	$RMSE_t(\rho_{s,L_5})$
AEKF-AR	0.0587	0.1047	0.0769
MAR-EKF	0.0605	0.1034	0.0740
Event #1	$RMSE_t(\theta_{s,L_1})$	$RMSE_t(\theta_{s,L_2})$	$RMSE_t(\theta_{s,L_5})$
AKF-AR	0.0800	0.1776	0.1698
AEKF-AR	0.0581	0.1035	0.0965
MAR-EKF	0.0456	0.0764	0.0551
Event #3	$RMSE_t(\rho_{s,L_1})$	$RMSE_t(\rho_{s,L_2})$	$RMSE_t(\rho_{s,L_5})$
AEKF-AR	0.0969	0.0933	0.0987
MAR-EKF	0.0784	0.0790	0.0771
Event #3	$RMSE_t(\theta_{s,L_1})$	$RMSE_t(\theta_{s,L_2})$	$RMSE_t(\theta_{s,L_5})$
AKF-AR	0.5044	0.4431	0.5202
AEKF-AR	0.3421	0.2916	0.2702
MAR-EKF	0.1968	0.1945	0.1916

Table 6. Root mean square scintillation components tracking error considering real scintillation data for the moderate scintillation event #1 ($t = 500 - 1000s$) and the severe scintillation event #3 ($t = 2000 - 2500s$).

377 In terms of cycle slips, the most challenging scenario is the severe scintillation event #6. We can
 378 see in Figure 5 that this event has the highest values for the scintillation index S_4 . We show the phase
 379 error for the different methods in Figure 9. While some cycle slips appear with the discriminator-
 380 based PLL, KF, AKF and AKF-AR, the methods including both scintillation components into the
 381 SSM formulation, AEKF-AR, MAR-EKF, are more robust (i.e., no cycle slips). These results con-

Fig. 9. Phase error for event #6, GPS L2.

	PLL	KF	AKF	AKF-AR	AEKF-AR	MAR-EKF
Event #6 L1	1	0	1	1	0	0
Event #6 L2	5	2	16	2	0	0
Event #6 L5	8	6	12	1	1	0

Table 7. Number of cycle slips for the real ionospheric scintillation event #6.

382 firm the enhanced filtering performance of the new approach. Notice that for this particular scenario,
 383 the number of cycle slips with the AKF is higher than with the standard PLL and KF. This is be-
 384 cause the filter is not able to cope with the strong fadings during severe scintillation due to the fast
 385 changes on the estimated C/N_0 , which controls the noise variance at the output of the discriminator.
 386 This is also the case with the discriminator-based AKF-AR, which does not take into account the
 387 scintillation amplitude. The number of cycle slips for event #6 and the three GPS frequency bands is
 388 shown in Table 7, which again confirm the superiority in terms of robustness of the new MAR-EKF.
 389

390 7. Conclusions

391 Carrier-phase measurements can be severely degraded due to ionospheric scintillation. This paper
 392 proposes a new tracking methodology that is able to extract the desired phase component, used
 393 for positioning, from the scintillation component. A key point is first to model both ionospheric
 394 scintillation components, amplitude and phase, using an AR model formulation, and then include
 395 them into the state to be tracked by the filter. This allows to decouple the phase contribution due to
 396 the LOS dynamics from the phase perturbations induced by the ionosphere. Particularly, we want

397 to exploit the advantages of multi-frequency architectures, because the scintillation characteristics
 398 are frequency-dependent. To take into account possible correlations among frequencies we must
 399 resort to multivariate AR models. A new state-space model is introduced and a Kalman-type state
 400 estimator operating on the outputs of the correlators implemented. The new method is validated
 401 using real scintillation data recorded in Hanoi, March and April 2015. It has been shown that the
 402 new filter outperforms state-of-the-art solutions in the tested scenarios, both in terms of mean square
 403 error and robustness to cycle slips. This approach provides a solution to the estimation/mitigation
 404 challenge when dealing with scintillation corrupted measurements.

405 One of the main challenges in the design of the proposed solution is the estimation of the multi-
 406 variate AR model parameters. While in the analysis conducted in this article these parameters have
 407 been obtained by fitting the desired model to a small part of the real time-series available (i.e., then
 408 processing a different part of the data), in real-life conditions, where the scintillation conditions
 409 evolve over time, we should consider an iterative procedure to adapt the filter to the actual work-
 410 ing conditions. Another important point is how to fix the LOS phase dynamics covariance matrix,
 411 which depends on the expected dynamics. To fully characterize the new method, it would be desir-
 412 able to have a larger set of data, recorded at different points over the earth, at different latitudes and
 413 containing several events. Even if the set of data available is representative of different scintillation
 414 conditions, it would be interesting to obtain a statistically more representative analysis.

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